

CULTURAL DIFFERENCES IN USING NONVERBAL MEANS IN COMMUNICATION

Dehqonboyeva Madina

Second-year student of Master's Degree
Andijan state institute of foreign languages
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14824742>

Annotation. This article studies verbal and nonverbal means of communication in linguistics. It discusses cultural differences of using nonverbal means in communication.

Keywords: communication, pragmatics, cultural differences, verbal and nonverbal means.

The participation of nonverbal tools in the speech process and their ability to express various nuances of meaning depending on the speaker's communicative goals are, on one hand, related to their pragmatic function, and on the other hand, to the cultural characteristics of the language speaker. The reason, function, relationship to the speech situation, and role in achieving pragmatic effect of nonverbal tools necessitate a discussion in the field of linguistic anthropology. Scholars have two main viewpoints regarding the cultural variation of nonverbal tools: the first group of scholars asserts that nonverbal tools are a universal language understandable by all humans, while others reject this idea. For instance, Charles Darwin defined gestures as innate and universal, Quintilian emphasized that hand movements are a common language for all humans, and scholars like Eibl-Eibesfeldt and A. Kostis also considered nonverbal tools to be universal. However, scholars like R. Birdwhistell, M. Argyle, P. Ekman, and D. Morris did not agree with this perspective [1].

Professor R. Birdwhistell emphasized that there are 250,000 facial expressions, which are manifested in two ways: common to all cultures and specific to each culture. However, due to the linguistic differences between cultures, nonverbal tools also exhibit cultural distinctions alongside verbal ones. In our view, nonverbal tools that reflect a person's inner emotions are universal for all, whereas a person's external relationship to the environment, their way of showing, explaining, or expressing their thoughts varies according to culture. Moreover, nonverbal tools reflecting inner emotions can be both innate and universal, while culturally differentiated gestures are linked to human behavior and upbringing. It would be appropriate to conditionally categorize them as natural and social nonverbal tools [2].

In today's globalization process, there is a growing demand for all nations and ethnic groups to consolidate and unite in pursuit of their common interests and goals. The struggle between good and evil has reached a new qualitative stage: the battle of ideas and concepts has intensified. Geographically speaking, the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan has historically been home to numerous representatives of different nations and ethnic groups, each with its own language, religion, culture, history, customs, and values. This, in turn, leads to linguistic diversity. These nations also have their own specific forms of verbal and nonverbal communication. It is well known that in sociolinguistics, intercultural communication and the study of nations help connect one nation with another. For this reason, intercultural communication, or more simply, the exchange of intercultural communication, is becoming increasingly important. Alongside the growing popularity of Uzbek customs, values, and communication culture, which are characteristic of the Uzbek people, the country provides all opportunities for other ethnic groups to develop their own languages and preserve their national and religious values [3].

It is also encouraging to see that representatives of other ethnicities and nations are respecting Uzbek national holidays, values, and traditions. In the process of following them, they are increasingly adopting nonverbal communication tools alongside verbal ones in their speech, which should be seen as a positive development. However, in Uzbek, there are certain subtle paralinguistic tools that may not be understood or recognized with ordinary communication time and scope. For instance, we can take as examples the celebrations of "Navruz – the common holiday," "Memory and Honor Day," or "Independence Day." In these rituals, representatives of various nationalities can be seen skillfully using paralinguistic tools in local, regional dialects, which is a reflection of nonverbal communication being established. For example, showing "the hand turning while stirring sumalak," "moving the hand vertically to wave the flag," "inviting to eat with the right hand fingers" and "greeting by placing the right hand on the chest" are gradually becoming part of the national etiquette of Uzbekistan [5].

However, it should be noted that some Uzbek regional customs and values might create misunderstandings among representatives of other nationalities or even among fellow Uzbeks if they are not familiar with them. Therefore, the growing interest in studying nonverbal tools that embody national culture, customs, and forms of speech is becoming increasingly important. It is worth highlighting the formation and development of fields like linguoanthropology

and linguoculturology in this context. Research has shown that paralinguistic tools are the most effective means of preserving national culture, customs, and values. They help convey subtle forms of communication that cannot easily be described with words to future generations. Additionally, nonverbal tools play a crucial role in understanding various art forms, such as music, theater, sculpture, painting, poetry, and craftsmanship.

Thus, nonverbal tools have become the object of research not only for linguists but also for sociologists, psychologists, cultural scholars, philosophers, historians, art critics, literary scholars, and professionals from other fields.

It should be noted that the culture, spirituality, and customs of each nation are defined by their contribution to universal human values and world civilization. Not only in the East but also worldwide, the national culture of the Uzbek people, one of the ancient nations, has a long history. Every action and condition of the Uzbeks is characterized by a wealth of life experience accumulated over centuries. Therefore, every nonverbal tool used in Uzbek communication serves to fully reveal the worldview, character, culture, spirituality, cognitive abilities, moods, and communicative intentions of the people. In other words, what a person wants to say is apparent in every gesture and facial expression. However, Americans' moods (whether good or bad) can only be determined from their smile, while it is more difficult to ascertain other aspects of their emotional state. They believe that a smile on the face during communication expresses respect and sincerity toward the conversation partner. On the other hand, the English tend to show seriousness, and the Russians are not accustomed to smiling without reason, as seriousness is predominant in their communication. In their view, constantly displaying politeness is seen as a way of hiding one's true character traits and, to some extent, expressing cunning.

The system of customs expressing nonverbal communication plays a crucial role in introducing the national culture of a people to the world. Some researchers consider nonverbal tools related to customs to be equivalent to language and attribute specific national meanings to them. For example, T. Nikolaeva suggests that national customs and culture, which have been passed down from generation to generation, should be studied just like language.

References:

1. Darwin Ch. The Expression of the Emotions in Man and Animals – London: John Murray. 1st edition, 1872; Eibl-Eibesfeldt. Ethology, the biology of behavior. Hold. – New York, 1970; Kostić A. Govor lica. Niš: Filozofski fakultet. 2006.

2. Ekman P. Emotional and conversational nonverbal signals. – Netherland, 2004. – P. 40; Burrow J. Gestures. In Gestures and Looks in Medieval Narrative. – Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. (Cambridge Studies in Medieval Literature, pp. 12), 2002. – P. 12; Michael Argyle. Bodily communication. – Cambridge University Press. – P. 75.
3. Stella Ting-Toomy. Communicating Across Cultures, First Edition. – New York, 1999.
4. Николаева Т., Успенский Б. Языкознание и паралингвистика // Лингвистические исследования по общей и славянской типологии. –М.: Наука, 1966. –С. 65.
5. Pazilova, N., & Iskhakova, A. (2023). ON THE STUDY OF PHRASEOLOGISMS IN MODERN ENGLISH. Models and methods in modern science, 2(12), 51-53.
6. Muhammadqosimovna, P. N. (2023). Semantic Peculiarities of Homonymy in English and Uzbek. Texas Journal of Philology, Culture and History, 14, 19-23.
7. Pazilova, N., & G'Opurova, X. (2022). Analysis of written and spoken texts in English and Uzbek. Science and innovation, 1(B8), 964-969.
8. Pazilova, N., & G'ofurova, G. (2022). SPECIFIC FEATURES AND THE PROBLEMS OF ALLITERATION IN MODERN ENGLISH AND UZBEK. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 1(5), 242-249.

